

EXPRESSION OF SIMILAR RELATION THROUGH SUPER SYNTACTIC INTEGRITY

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Abstract: This article examines the expression of the relationship of analogy across language levels using various linguistic means, which allows us to determine whether they have a unique system and provide information about their specific semantic and stylistic features.

Keywords: analogy, relationship, text, super syntactic whole, speech.

In world linguistics, many scientific studies have been conducted on the relationship of analogy. As a result of the analysis of the initial scientific studies, it was shown that the relationship of analogy has historically been approached as one of the most important methods of the cognitive process, a philosophical-logical category. Later, the emergence of structuralism in linguistics led to a new look at the study of the relationship of analogy. Thus, in a different approach to the study of the relationship of analogy, the main attention was paid to the study of its semantic process, the analysis and study of its means. In addition, the discovery that this relationship consists of several elements prompted the study of its unique expression in various language units.

Analogy is “based on the similarity between two objects or events, one of them expresses the sign, essence of the other more fully, more specifically, more vividly”. Similes, as one of the oldest figurative means, have been used to decorate our speech, especially the language of fiction, and to ensure the clarity and imagery of the image.

Initially, the largest syntactic unit in linguistics was considered to be a sentence, and later, in the 70s-80s of the 20th century, it was proven that there is a speech unit larger than a sentence - a microtext - a supersyntactic whole.

The text and its types were studied primarily by cognitive psychology as a socially communicative speech unit. Later, the development of cognitive linguistics became the basis for approaching it as a language unit. Brinker divides this study process into three stages:

1. The stage of studying the communicative-pragmatic properties of the text.
2. The stage of studying the topic (context) of the text.
3. The stage of studying the linguistic-stylistic properties of the text (syntactic3.1 -stylistic relations).

It was the research conducted by European and Russian linguists on text linguistics that became the main impetus for the development of this field in Uzbek linguistics.

The initial information about the text in Uzbek linguistics was the report on the theory of text made by G. Abdurakhmonov at the All-Union Scientific Conference of Turkologists held in Tashkent in 1980, which became the basis for the emergence of text linguistics in Uzbek linguistics. After that, the research conducted by such scientists as I. Rasulov, M. Askarova, A. Mamajonov, N. Turniyazov, M. Khakimov, M. Yuldashev, M. Kurbanova, M. Abdupattoev, D. Khudoiberganova, U. Nasirova contributed to the development of this field.

The research conducted expressed the idea that the content of the text, in particular, the comparative content, is also expressed through the supersyntactic whole, the large unit of the text.

In her scientific work on the anthropocentric study of the text, D. Khudoyberganova studied the linguistic-cultural characteristics of the texts and their place in the creation of the text.

“The text is the largest expression of speech with a specific complex syntactic structure, which in a broad sense represents a whole work, and in a narrow sense - a

supersyntactic whole.” Professor A. Mamajonov, in his research on text linguistics, states that the text consists of the following units:

- sentence;
- supersyntactic whole;
- paragraph;
- period.

A supersyntactic whole is a speech unit that is larger than a microtextual form of a sentence and smaller than a literary work. “Each supersyntactic whole is a miniature story that represents an event that has its own beginning, development and ending.” The first sentence of a supersyntactic whole is called the theme and it represents the main idea. The sentences in the supersyntactic whole are interconnected and reveal a certain semantic relationship. It has the following semantic relations, as in compound sentences: time-condition, condition-impedance, cause-effect, comparison-contrast, and analogy.

It is clear that in languages, the relationship of analogy can also be expressed through a super-syntactic unity. When the relationship of analogy is expressed through this unity, the properties of two objects are likened to each other.

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